

Utilizing AI and Attention to Assist in Training Medical Students to Read and Diagnose Electrocardiograms

Hartley P. J.¹[0009-0006-0736-5100], Edwards J.²[0009-0000-5819-1709] and MacInnes W. J.³[0000-0002-5134-1601]

¹ Swansea University, Swansea SA1 8EN, UK

² Swansea University, Swansea SA1 8EN, UK

³ Swansea University, Swansea SA1 8EN, UK
lncs@springer.com

Electrocardiograms allow for the diagnosis and analysis of cardiovascular conditions. Despite this, there is a lack of consistent analytical strategies. This results in newer medical practitioners, often students, fixating on irrelevant segments. This leads to frequent misdiagnosis and a high level of inconsistencies. By using machine learning strategies and analyzing human attention networks, recorded through the medium of eye-tracking, we hope to develop a tool to aid medical students and medical practitioners in making consistent and accurate electrocardiogram diagnoses.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Electrocardiogram, Attention.

1 Electrocardiograms

The heart can be understood as a pump transporting blood around the body that is powered by the electrical activity of specialized cells within the heart [1]. An electrocardiogram (ECG) records this electrical activity via 12 “leads” attached to a patient’s chest. Indications for carrying out an ECG are varied, including the investigation of symptoms, the monitoring of patients, and patient assessment before surgery. A 12-lead ECG is comprised of six chest leads, that provide a picture of the transverse plane of the heart, six limb leads, that give a view of the vertical plane, and a longer “rhythm strip” that displays a ten-second recording from a single lead and is used to determine the overall rhythm of the heartbeat, this is most commonly Lead II [2].

Healthcare professionals are usually taught to take a systematic approach to interpreting ECGs. They first determine the rate, either by calculating the distance between the R waves, or the number of R waves in the rhythm strip [1]. Rhythm is then assessed by examining the regularity of the R waves, the presence or absence of P waves, the distance between the P wave and the start of the QRS complex (PR interval), and the width of the QRS complex, usually 120ms [1]. The cardiac axis is next determined by the polarity of the P waves, inverse or upright. Finally, there is the interpretation of the height of the segment between the S and T waves (ST Segment) and the prolongation

or truncation of time between the Q and T segments (QT Interval), before the morphology of each wave is examined further.

This level of diagnostic complexity should highlight the importance and need for assistive tools for the training of new medical practitioners and the diagnosis of cardiovascular conditions. Not only will this save the practitioner time, but it will also allow for a more consistent and accurate diagnosis.

2 MIMIC-IV-ECG Dataset

The MIMIC-IV-ECG Dataset [3] is a 12-lead, 10-second dataset containing 800,000 diagnostic ECGs. Each ECG sample was recorded at a frequency of 500hz. This dataset can be linked to the MIMIC-IV open-access electronic health record dataset [4] which contains a wide variety of data types that were recorded at the same time/around the same time as the ECG data. This could assist us with improving the diagnostic capabilities of machine learning models. While the dataset contained a variety of diagnoses, we opted only to include the four most prominent conditions. These were Sinus Rhythm, Sinus Bradycardia, Sinus Tachycardia, and Atrial Fibrillation.

3 Image Analysis

A key aspect of this project was to attempt to imitate the way humans process ECGs. For this reason, we opted to convert the data from raw ECG data into image format, see **Fig.1**. This could be used to give us key insights into how a neural network might handle the task compared to a medical practitioner and could also assist in the creation of an interactive tool for training medical students. Future work on this project will also include defining regions of interest based on eye movements. Therefore, the utilization of image neural networks lends itself well to this additional aspect of the project.

Fig. 1. Example of plotted 12-lead, 10-second diagnostic Electrocardiogram

4 Convolutional Neural Network

The algorithm we utilized was a generic image Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) implemented through PyTorch [7], this was done so it could be utilized as a baseline to compare the effectiveness of future algorithms. For each of the 4 conditions, we selected 30,000 samples from the dataset, this resulted in a total count of 120,000 samples. The dataset was divided into the train, and test sets by utilizing 100,000 samples for training and 20,000 samples for testing

Despite not having high hopes for the baseline algorithm (CNN), it produced a promising accuracy of 79%. By breaking the accuracy down based on classes, we can see individual accuracies of; Sinus Rhythm at 64.07%, Sinus Bradycardia at 91.48%, Sinus Tachycardia at 87.00%, and Atrial Fibrillation at 74.32%. This shows that accuracy is brought down by the CNN struggling to classify the Sinus Rhythm and Atrial Fibrillation tasks, specifically Sinus Rhythm. This could indicate that the current algorithm cannot accurately distinguish between the two tasks. However, more insight is needed before a conclusion can be drawn. To improve this accuracy, our next steps will be to implement other image neural networks such as the Spatially-Sparse Convolutional Network [8] which has seen promising results in classifying medical imaging [9].

5 Attention for Students and Medical Practitioners

Several eye-tracking studies into the interpretation of ECGs have compared the approaches of students and experienced practitioners. Experts tend to be more successful at correctly interpreting ECGs than novices, and experts and novices consistently employ different interpretation strategies [10]. Where novices tend to fixate on abnormal-looking areas, which can often be irrelevant and lead to misdiagnosis, experts tend to be more effective at discerning which patterns are relevant. However, the behaviors of each group are not always consistent between studies, notably with the presence, or absence, of a systematic approach [11]. Furthermore, participants have reported that they employ a particular approach to interpretation, which has not been borne out by eye-tracking data, suggesting a lack of insight when it comes to successful strategies. The studies to date have suffered from small sample sizes, perhaps this would account for the inconsistencies in the strategies and methods employed. A machine learning agent, when trained to read an ECG in a manner akin to a human, provides the opportunity to understand successful interpretation strategies based on much larger amounts of data. This can then inform the training of healthcare professionals with the hope that they will be able to consistently and accurately interpret ECGs in a clinical setting.

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